

ASH DIEBACK MONITORING IN LOWER AUSTRIA

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Ash dieback causes damage and mortality of *Fraxinus excelsior* (common ash) and *Fraxinus angustifolia* (narrow-leaved ash) in Europe. In Austria, the first symptoms of the disease caused by the fungus *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus* (anamorph *Chalara fraxinea*) were recorded in 2005. To study the development and etiology, 14 permanent monitoring plots were installed in various parts of Lower Austria and continuously monitored almost every year since. Twenty mature ash trees per plot were assessed between July and August. The affected crown volume was visually estimated on a 5 % scale. In 2016 the mean crown dieback intensity of the remaining 248 trees was compared to their first assessment in 2008 showing an increase from 11% to 29%. Mean damage of the least affected plots also increased from 1% in 2008 to 11% in 2016. The most affected plot in 2008 remained the most severely damaged plot in 2016 with a mean value increase from 34 % to 71 %. Overall, mortality was low with 4 % and observed in five out of the 14 plots. Work is in progress to relate the long-term observation of ash dieback to climatic data.